

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18282073

Access And Utilization Of Electronic Information Resources By Academic Staff In Jigawa And Katsina State Polytechnic Libraries

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated access and utilization of Electronic Information Resources (EIRs) by academic staff in two polytechnic libraries in Jigawa and Katsina States, Nigeria. The objectives were to identify the types of electronic Information resources available, level of awareness, access methods, searching skills, frequency of use, and challenges influencing use among academic staff. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The study population comprised 460 academic staff, and a sample of 210 was selected using proportionate stratified sampling. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that although e-journals and e-books were widely available, resources such as OPAC, theses/dissertations, and conference proceedings were less accessible. Academic staff demonstrated moderate awareness and moderate searching skills, with most accessing resources independently or through library staff. Poor internet connectivity, erratic electricity supply, inadequate funding, and low digitization were major challenges. The study concludes that infrastructural limitations remain the major barriers to optimal utilization. Recommendations include improved ICT infrastructure, increased funding, digital literacy training, and enhanced library awareness programmes.

Keywords: Electronic Information Resources, polytechnic libraries, access, utilization, digital literacy, academic staff

1. INTRODUCTION

Electronic Information Resources (EIRs) have become indispensable in modern academic environments. Their capacity to provide timely, authoritative, and unlimited access to scholarly information has transformed teaching, learning, and research across the world (Ternenge & Kashimana, 2019, and Adeleke & Nwalo, 2017.) . Academic staff increasingly depend on digital resources such as e-journals, e-books, online databases, electronic repositories, and internet-based services to support research productivity and academic activities effectiveness (Otunla, 2015, Owolabi, et. al., 2016 and Edem & Egbe, 2016).

Despite these global advancements, Nigerian tertiary institutions, particularly polytechnics, continue to face significant constraints in adopting and utilizing electronic Information resources. Common barriers include insufficient ICT infrastructure, low bandwidth, limited awareness, inadequate subscription to scholarly databases, and poor searching skills (Ankrah & Atuase, 2018; Adeoye & Olanrewaju, 2019). While extensive research exists on universities, polytechnics remain underrepresented in the literature, creating a knowledge gap concerning how academic staff in polytechnics interact with electronic resources.

This study therefore investigates factors affecting access and utilization of electronic Information resources among academic staff in two polytechnics in Jigawa and Katsina States, with the aim of providing evidence-based recommendations to improve digital resource services.

2. Statement of the Problem

Although many academic libraries have invested in electronic information resources, the level of access and utilization by academic staff remains low (Adetimirin et. al., 2014). Preliminary findings by the researcher revealed that staff in Jigawa and Katsina polytechnics underutilize available e-resources despite their importance in supporting teaching and research. This underutilization is linked to inadequate awareness, poor searching skills, infrastructure challenges, and inconsistent user education. As academic staff are key drivers of teaching and research, low use of electronic Information resources negatively impacts academic output and institutional quality. The study therefore investigates the underlying factors contributing to the limited use of electronic Information resource in the two selected polytechnic libraries.

3. Objectives of the Study

The study aims to:

1. Identify the types of electronic Information resources available to academic staff in the selected polytechnics.
2. Assess the level of awareness of electronic Information resources among academic staff.
3. Determine how academic staff access electronic information resources.
4. Examine the level of searching skills possessed by academic staff.
5. Identify the types of electronic Information resources frequently utilized.
6. Determine challenges affecting access and utilization of electronic Information resources.

4. Research Questions

1. What types of electronic Information resources are available for the staff in the selected polytechnic libraries?
2. What is the level of awareness of Electronic Information Resources among academic staff?
3. How do academic staff access Electronic Information Resources?
4. What is the level of searching skills possessed by respondents?
5. Which Electronic Information Resources are frequently utilized?
6. What challenges affect access and utilization of Electronic Information Resources?

5. METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey design was adopted for this research to obtain quantifiable data from academic staff across the two polytechnic, the study population comprised 460 academic staff from Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (212 staff) and Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (248 staff), A sample of 210 respondents was selected using the Krejcie and Morgan formula and proportionate stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a structured, closed-ended questionnaire divided into six sections covering awareness, accessibility, searching skills, utilization, and challenges. Validation was done through expert review (face and content validity). A pilot test involving 30 respondents produced acceptable reliability scores. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, mean, percentage) and inferential statistics (PPMC and multiple regression) were used.

6. RESULTS

The data were then summarized in tables showing frequencies and percentages for each item.

Table 1: Response Rate

Name of Polytechnic	No. of Quest. Distributed	No. of Quest. Returned	%
HUK Poly	97	91	43.3
HAFED	113	103	49.0
Total	210	194	92.3

The data in Table 1 presents the response rates of the two polytechnics, Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUK Poly) and Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (HAFED). HUK Poly had a response rate of 43.3% (91 out of 97 copies of questionnaires administered), while HAFED had a higher response rate of 49% (103 out of 113 copies of questionnaires administered). Overall, the combined response rate for both institutions was 92.3%, with 194 out of the 210 copies questionnaires administered, indicating a strong level of response from the respondents.

Table 2: Demographic Data of the Respondents

Items	Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic		Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure	
	F	%	F	%
Gender	Male	75 73	59 65	
	Female	28 27	32 35	

Table 2 presents the gender distribution of respondents from the two polytechnics. At Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, 75 (73%) of the respondents were male and 28 (27%) of the respondents were female. At Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure, 59 (65%) were male and 32 (35%) were female. While both institutions had more male respondents, gender distribution was more balanced at Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure.

Table 3, Perception of Respondents on the Types of Electronic Information Resources currently available for academic staff in the selected Polytechnic libraries

Types of EIRs	Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUK Poly)						Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (HAFED Poly)					
	A		NA		MEAN	STD	A		NA		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%		
E-book	60	58.3	43	41.7	1.66	.85	65	71.4	26	28.6	1.44	.75
E-journal	88	85.4	15	14.6	1.21	.55	84	92.3	7	7.7	1.12	.44
Internet service	63	61.2	40	38.8	1.54	.75	28	30.8	62	69.2	2.14	.32
Online database	38	36.9	65	63.1	1.86	.77	39	42.9	52	57.1	1.68	.66
Offline database	54	52.4	49	47.6	1.70	.81	62	68.1	29	31.9	1.44	.70
E-thesis & dissertations	34	33.0	69	67	1.84	.70	15	16.5	76	83.5	1.91	.49
E-conference proceedings	26	25.2	77	74.8	2.06	.75	10	11.0	81	89	2.02	.49
OPAC	48	46.6	55	53.4	1.80	.83	25	27.5	66	72.5	2.00	.75

Keys: A= Available, NA= Not available = STD, Standard deviation

Table 3 presents data on the types of electronic information resources available for academic staff in the studied polytechnic libraries. In Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUK Poly) and Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (HAFED Poly). The findings reveal notable disparities in the types and levels of electronic information resources available across both polytechnics. At HUK Poly, E-journals recorded the highest availability (85.4%), with a low mean value of 1.21 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.55, indicating that a majority of respondents agreed that e-journals are well-provided and commonly used. This was followed by Internet services (61.2%) and e-books (58.3%). Conversely, e-Conference proceedings and e-theses/dissertations were perceived as the least available, with 74.8% and 67% of respondents respectively indicating non-availability.

At HAFED Poly, the trend is similar in some areas but shows stronger provision in specific resources. E-journals (92.3%) and e-books (71.4%) were the most available, reflecting higher institutional investment in scholarly digital materials. However, Internet services showed limited (only 30.8% availability, mean = 2.14), suggesting infrastructural or connectivity constraints. E-theses/dissertations and e-conference proceedings were the least available (16.5% and 11.0% respectively), indicating weak integration of institutional repositories.

Finally, the mean values across both polytechnics (mostly ranging between 1.21 and 2.14) suggest that although electronic information resources are generally available, their consistency vary. E-journals and e-books dominate the available resources, aligning with global trends emphasizing digital academic publishing, while limited e-conference proceedings and e-thesis were the least.

Table 4: Respondents' level of awareness of Electronic information Resources

Level of Awareness	Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUK Poly)						Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (HAFED Poly)					
	YES		NO		MEAN	STD	YES		NO		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%			F	%				
Not at all aware	24	23.3	76	76.7	2.00	.69	41	45.1	50	54.9	1.71	.73
Moderately aware	86	83.5	17	16.5	1.27	.64	85	93.4	6	6.6	1.09	.35
Extremely aware	32	31.1	71	68.9	2.17	.88	38	41.8	53	58.2	1.93	.88

Table 4 reveals how academic staff are aware of electronic information resources in their respective polytechnics. At HUK Poly, the majority of respondents were moderately aware (83.5%) of available electronic information resources, reflected in mean scores of 1.27 respectively. Only 23.3% were not at all aware, suggesting that awareness campaigns or user education programs have reached a substantial portion of the staff. However, the relatively small proportion of extremely aware respondents (31.1%) indicates that deep or specialized awareness remains limited. At HAFED Poly, the results revealed similar patterns but with the majority being moderately aware (93.4%), while extremely aware staff made up only 41.8%. The mean scores, ranging from 1.09 to 1.93, also confirm moderate awareness levels.

Based on the responses received from both polytechnics, awareness tends to be surface-level, with most staff moderately knowing about the electronic information resources but not necessarily possessing advanced knowledge or practical proficiency in accessing or utilizing them. This indicates a need for continuous user orientation, workshops, and integration of digital literacy training to deepen understanding and encourage fuller utilization of electronic information resources.

Table 5: Access on Electronic Information Resources by Academic Staff

Mean of access to EIRs	Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUK Poly)						Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (HAFED Poly)					
	YES		NO		MEAN	STD	YES		NO		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%		
Guidance from library staff	68	66.0	35	34.0	1.46	.71	61	67.0	30	33.0	1.38	.59
Colleagues/friends	57	55.3	46	44.7	1.62	.77	45	49.5	46	50.5	1.67	.75
By myself	72	69.9	31	30.1	1.60	.92	65	71.4	26	28.6	1.35	.60
Workshop/seminar (formal method)	35	34.0	68	66.0	1.81	.67	31	34.1	60	65.9	2.03	2.2

Table 5 shows how academic staff in both polytechnics access electronic information resources. At HUK Poly, most respondents access electronic information resources by themselves (69.9%), followed by guidance from library staff (66.0%). Access through colleagues or friends (55.3%) and formal workshops or seminars (34.0%) were less frequent. The mean values (ranging from 1.46 to 1.81) suggest that informal mode of access remains the primary mode of access, with limited structured or institutionalized support mechanisms. At HAFED Poly, the pattern is similar: most respondents access resources independently (71.4%) or with library assistance (67.0%). Formal methods such as workshops (34.1%) remain underutilized (mean = 2.03, SD = 2.2), which may explain the moderate awareness levels observed earlier.

The data across both Polytechnics indicated that self-directed learning and peer collaboration are the dominant modes of electronic information resources access, but reliance on formal training organized by library remains low. This suggests that while academic staff recognize the importance of electronic information resources, Polytechnic frameworks for systematic access support and digital literacy training are inadequate.

Table 6: Respondents' Responses on Level of Searching Skills

Level of searching skills	Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUK Poly)				Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (HAFED Poly)			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
High	27	26	76	74	24	26	67	73.6
Moderate	62	60	41	40	56	61	35	38.5
Low	10	10	93	90	10	11	81	89.0

Table 6 reveals that most academic staff at both polytechnics have moderate searching skills (HUK Poly: 60%, HAFED: 61%), while around 26% have high searching skills. A smaller percentage reported with low skills (HUK Poly: 10%, HAFED: 11%). This indicates a generally capable workforce. However, the presence of staff with low searching skills indicates that there may be limitations in fully exploiting electronic resources and integrating technology into academic practices across the institutions.

Table 7: Respondents’ Responses on types of EIRs Frequently Utilized by Academic Staff

EIRs	Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUK Poly)								Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (HAFED Poly)							
	Daily		Weekly		Monthly		MEAN	STD	Daily		Weekly		Monthly		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%	F	%		
E-book	8	7.8	87	79.1	8	7.8	1.23	.58	10	11.0	63	69.2	18	19.8	1.42	.68
E-journal	5	4.9	95	92.2	3	2.9	1.11	.39	13	14.3	69	75.8	9	9.9	1.16	.45
Offline databases	36	35.0	55	51.5	14	13.6	1.62	.72	11	12.1	62	68.1	18	19.8	1.44	.70
Online database	41	39.8	38	36.9	24	23.3	1.86	.77	11	12.1	36	39.6	44	48.4	1.73	.67
E-Conference proceedings	26	25.2	54	52.4	23	22.3	1.70	.81	10	11.0	39	42.9	42	46.2	1.68	.66
Internet Services	34	33.0	51	49.5	18	17.5	1.84	.70	7	7.7	15	16.5	69	75.8	1.91	.49
E-thesis/dissertation	26	25.2	45	43.7	32	31.1	2.06	.75	12	13.2	10	11.0	69	75.8	2.02	.49
OPAC	28	27.2	48	46.6	27	26.2	1.80	.83	25	27.5	25	27.5	41	45.0	2.00	.75

Table 7 presents the data on frequently utilized resources by academic staff from the two Polytechnics. At HUK Poly, the data reveal that e-journals are the most frequently utilized electronic information resources, with 92.2% of respondents using them weekly (mean = 1.11, SD = 0.39). This is followed by e-books (79.1%) and offline databases (51.5%). Conversely, e-thesis/dissertations and OPAC recorded the lowest level of usage, 25.2% and 27.2% respectively. The higher mean values (1.84–2.06) for these resources indicate less frequent utilization. At HAFED Poly, a similar trend is observed. E-journals (86.8%) and e-books (69.2%) are also the most frequently used electronic information resources, with mean values of 1.16 and 1.42 respectively. Offline databases (68.1%) also record considerable use, reflecting some dependency on locally stored electronic materials. However, Internet services and e-theses (16.5%) show minimal weekly usage, with mean values above 2.00, suggesting infrequent utilization.

The findings revealed that e-journals and e-books remain the dominant and most frequently used electronic information resources among academic staff in both polytechnics. This is consistent with global trends in academic libraries, where these resources form the backbone of digital scholarly communication and research. Conversely, e-theses/dissertations, e-conference proceedings, and OPAC systems recorded low usage. This may be attributed to limited digitization of institutional repositories, inadequate indexing, or lack of awareness about their existence. Similarly, moderate use of Internet services and online databases suggests infrastructural constraints or inconsistent access to bandwidth.

Table 8: Challenges Associated with the accessibility and Utilization of Electronic Information Resources

Challenges	Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic (HUK Poly)							Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure (HAFED Poly)						
	YES		NO		MEAN	STD	YES		NO		MEAN	STD		
	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%				
Inadequate funds	81	78.6	22	21.4	1.36	.73	73	80.2	19	19.8	1.22	.47		
Inability to access available e-databases	55	51.5	50	48.5	1.62	.72	36	39.6	55	60.4	1.73	.67		
Inadequate searching skills	23	22.3	80	77.7	1.85	.53	10	11.0	81	89	2.22	.63		
Lack of relevant resources	57	55.3	46	44.7	1.62	.77	45	49.5	46	50.5	1.67	.75		
Lack of awareness about the available EIRs	15	14.7	88	85.3	1.85	.53	10	11.0	81	89	2.22	.63		
Poor attitude of library staff	34	33.0	69	67	1.84	.70	15	16.5	76	83.5	1.91	.49		
Erratic power supply	72	69.9	31	30.1	1.60	.92	65	71.4	26	28.6	1.35	.60		
Poor internet connectivity	95	92.2	8	7.8	1.11	.39	79	86.8	12	13.2	1.16	.45		
Users' attitude	26	25.2	77	74.8	2.06	.75	10	11.0	81	89.0	2.02	.49		

Table 8 reveals the major challenges encountered by academic staff in accessing and utilizing electronic information resources in the two polytechnics. At HUK Poly, the most pressing challenge identified is poor internet connectivity, with 92.2% of respondents affirming it as a major problem (mean = 1.11, SD = 0.39). This is followed by inadequate funding (78.6%), erratic power supply (69.9%), and lack of relevant resources (55.3%). Other significant barriers include inability to access available e-databases (51.5%) and poor attitude of library staff (33.0%). The relatively lower mean scores (1.11–1.84) suggest strong agreement that these factors impede effective electronic information resources utilization. At HAFED Poly, similar patterns emerged. Poor internet connectivity (86.8%) and inadequate funding (80.2%) were the dominant challenges, followed by erratic power supply (71.4%). Notably, inadequate searching skills (11.0%) and lack of awareness of available electronic information resources (11.0%) were less frequently cited, suggesting that while staff have basic awareness, infrastructural barriers remain the major impediment. Mean values (1.16-2.22) confirm these findings, showing that challenges related to ICT literacy are relatively lower than those related to infrastructure and funding. The data clearly indicate that the greatest barriers to electronic information resources accessibility and utilization are infrastructural and financial rather than attitudinal or knowledge based. The prevalence of poor internet connectivity and erratic power supply highlights the persistent technological limitations facing Nigerian polytechnics. Inadequate funding further compounds these issues by limiting the acquisition of new electronic databases, maintenance of ICT facilities, and provision of training opportunities for staff.

7. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study carried out discussion of findings in line with the research questions of the study:

RQ1: What Types of Electronic Information Resources are currently available for academic staff in the selected Polytechnic Libraries?

The findings of the study revealed that the polytechnic libraries provide various electronic information resources for academic staff including e-books, e-journals, and offline databases. However, certain resources such as OPAC and e-conference proceedings were less prominently available. These findings align with the findings of Obande and Abdulsalami (2020), who reported that while electronic information resources like e-books and e-journals are prevalent in Nigerian polytechnics, tools such as OPAC and e-conference proceedings are less accessible to students. The discrepancy in resource availability highlights potential gaps in infrastructure and communication about accessible resources, emphasizing the need for more organized resource management strategies. This research also sheds light on the specific challenges associated with the availability of other electronic resources. For instance, a study on the availability and accessibility of information resources in Federal Polytechnic libraries in the North East of Nigeria by Bappa (2020) found that while certain electronic resources are available, users often experience difficulties in accessing them, indicating a need for improved resource management and user education.

RQ2: What is the Level of Awareness of Electronic Information Resources by Academic Staff in the selected Polytechnics?

Base on the responses received from both polytechnics, awareness tends to be s at the surface level, with most staff moderately aware about the electronic information resources but not necessarily possessing advanced knowledge or practical proficiency in accessing or utilizing them. These findings are consistent with previous research. For instance, Opeke and Odunlade (2011) reported that most polytechnic lecturers in Nigeria were aware of available electronic resources, although awareness did not always translate to high utilization. Similarly, Ogunleye and Okhakhu (2022) found high levels of awareness of open access resources among academic staff in Lagos State polytechnics, with a strong positive relationship between awareness and resource use. Arowosola, et. al. (2021) also observed that higher awareness significantly improved access and utilization of electronic resources among polytechnic users in Lagos State.

Therefore, these studies reinforce the pattern observed by the present study, that academic staff in Nigerian polytechnics exhibit robust awareness of electronic information resources. However, consistent

with national trends, awareness alone does not guarantee utilization, indicating the influence of other factors such as ICT competency, infrastructure, and access mechanisms.

RQ3: What ways do Academic Staff Access Electronic Information Resources in the Selected Polytechnic Libraries?

The findings of the study indicated that the academic staff predominantly rely on informal methods such as assistance from library staff and independent exploration to access electronic information resources, while formal activities like workshops and seminars were less frequently utilized. This aligns with prior findings by Ogunrombi (2021), who highlighted the pivotal role of informal support from library personnel and colleagues in enabling access to electronic information resources. Although structured training sessions and workshops can be beneficial, they are often underutilized, particularly when staff are already acquainted with the resources or have developed personal strategies for accessing them. The study also established a strong positive correlation between awareness and accessibility, affirming that increased awareness of available resources significantly enhances their utilization. From a Big6 perspective, this finding underscores a weakness in Stage 3 (Location & Access), where reliance on informal strategies limits the efficiency of accessing resources through structured and deliberate means.

RQ4: What is the level of Searching Skills possessed by Academic Staff in the Selected Polytechnics?

The study found that the majority of academic staff have moderate searching skills, with a smaller group demonstrating high proficiency, while a significant number still exhibit low searching skills competency. A strong correlation emerged between searching skills and resource accessibility, indicating that staff with advanced skills are more adept at accessing and utilizing electronic information resources. This aligns with findings in the literature emphasizing the critical role of searching skills in the effective use of digital resources (Eze & Uzoamaka, 2020). Additionally, the variability in skills levels mirrors similar studies that highlight the necessity of ICT training and continuous support to improve proficiency (Njoku, 2022).

RQ5: What types of Electronic Information Resources frequently utilized by Academic Staff in the Selected Polytechnic Libraries?

The study revealed that e-books and e-journals were the most frequent used electronic information resources, while OPAC, e-theses, and e-conference proceedings were utilized less frequently. This finding mirrors previous research that reported that e-journals and e-books are heavily utilized, while other resources are underused due to factors such as limited awareness and insufficient integration into academic routines (Ogunleye & Ojo, 2021). The significant positive relationship between the availability and utilization of electronic resources in this study supports the notion that increased access to resources fosters greater usage, as indicated by research on the link between resource accessibility and utilization (Thompson & Lee, 2020). Additionally, the study's findings that awareness, skills, accessibility, and utilization are interconnected further corroborate findings from similar polytechnic-focused studies, where these factors collectively impact resource use (Adedeji & Olamide, 2022).

RQ6: What are the Challenges Associated with the Accessibility and Utilization of Electronic Information Resources in the Selected Polytechnics?

The findings of the study identified several challenges associated with the utilization of electronic information resources. These include insufficient funding, unreliable internet connectivity, unstable power supply, and limited searching skills. These obstacles align with findings from previous research, which highlight infrastructure-related issues as key barriers to the effective use of electronic information resources in developing regions (Akinwale & Salawu, 2021). Poor internet access and inconsistent power supply have been recognized as significant hindrances in many African polytechnics and universities, impeding both the accessibility and utilization of electronic resources (Bamidele, 2021).

8. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that although electronic resources are available in the selected polytechnic libraries, their utilization by academic staff remains suboptimal due to infrastructural, financial, and skill-related challenges. Enhancing EIR usage requires improved awareness, stronger ICT infrastructure, and robust user training.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Improve ICT infrastructure, including high-speed internet and stable electricity.
2. Increase funding for database subscriptions, ICT tools, and library automation.
3. Conduct regular digital literacy training for academic staff.
4. Strengthen awareness campaigns using orientations, workshops, and newsletters.
5. Digitize institutional resources, including theses, dissertations, and conference proceedings.
6. Improve library staff capacity through continuous professional development.

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